

ENHANCING SCIENCE LITERACY ON SELECTED TOPIC IN EARTH AND LIFE SCIENCE THROUGH ELECTRONIC STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL (E-SIM)

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the effectiveness of Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIM) in enhancing science literacy, particularly in Earth and Life Science topics. It aims to improve students' knowledge and recall of scientific concepts through interactive electronic media. A t-test analysis revealed a highly significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results, with a computed p-value of 0.00000000453663, indicating substantial improvement in students who received the e-SIM intervention. The findings suggest that e-SIM is a valuable tool for enhancing science literacy and offer teachers a promising approach for integrating technology into science instruction. While the study highlights the potential of electronic interventions in improving student performance, it also recommends further research on the long-term impact of e-SIM on students' retention and practical application of scientific knowledge.

Keywords: *Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (e-SIM), Science Literacy, Earth and Life Science, Interactive media*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID 19 pandemic brought a sudden change in many areas of our life, especially on education sector – both formal and non-formal learning environments. Amidst the pandemic, the Department of Education also shifted its gear. The Department of Education released the DepEd Order No. 12, s.2020 known as the Adoption of Basic

Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) for the School Year 2020 – 2021 considering the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. The aim of the department is to supply an intervention that answers to the basic education brought the pandemic. Furthermore, the Department of Education thru the BELCP reiterated the means of supplying different learning opportunities through different learning modalities.

Along with the COVID19 threat, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 2018 reported that Filipino students ranking the lowest among 79 countries in mathematics, science, and reading. Villegas (2021) addressed that in subjects' math and science, 15-year-old Filipino students obtained 353 points in science and 357 points in mathematics, contrary to the 489 OECD average for both categories.

Furthermore, based on the 2018 PISA report, 15-year-old Filipino learners obtained lower scores in reading, mathematics, and science as compared to other countries took part on PISA 2018. Hence, further reiterated that 80% of Filipino learners did not meet the minimum level of ability in reading.

Alongside PISA, the Trends in Mathematics and Science Studies conducted an international test in 2019. The TIMSS reported that Philippine Science and Mathematics education are deteriorating. Based on the TIMSS 2019 report, Philippines has the lowest math and science score among the fifty-eight countries involved.

With the reports, the Department of Education are doing their best to elevate the educational status of the country in terms of mathematics and science education. DepEd are reskilling and retooling their teachers here and out. Furthermore, the BE-LCP reiterated that the intervention delivery shall be multi-modal approach that influences accessible technology.

Since the pandemic started, Science literacy is starting to deteriorate. With this, teachers are using intervention materials for the learners to cope and grasp the lesson aims.

Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) is defined as instructional material that helps learner master the competency-based skills which were not able to master within the regular class.

The SIM was composed of various parts – the Title Card, the Overview, the Objective Card, the Guide Card, Activity Card, Assessment Card, Enrichment Card, Reference Card, and Answer Key Card. Different research shows that SIM are immense help for remediating students.

Salviejo, Aranes, and Espinosa (2014) conducted research entitled Strategic Intervention Material-Based Instruction, Learning Approach and Students' Performance in Chemistry wherein the researchers concluded that learning Chemistry with the help of SIM is fun, enjoyable, and interesting.

Dacumos (2016) concluded that strategically planned and creatively crafted SIM integration in classroom practice, teaching science and facilitation will effectively become the tool for learners' understanding and appreciation of many concepts in science. Diaz and Dio (2017) gleaned the fact that when students are exposed to SIM, their Mathematics achievements are better and higher.

Santos (2019) said that the results supported the feasibility and practicality of utilizing SIMATAR (SIM in Teaching with Augmented Reality) as a teaching tool in addition to the traditional firsthand minds-on laboratory activities. Hence, it was seen that the use of a mobile augmented reality application in teaching yielded high engagement among students and improved their time on-task compared with non-digital learning activities.

Adonis (2020) further claimed under her study that contextualized SIM helped low performing students gain mastery of the least learned competency.

Luzano (2020) reiterated on his research entitled Development and Validation of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) of the Selected Topics in Trigonometry of Precalculus Discipline in Senior High School that SIMs provide hope for the STEM students who generally have a bad impression of Trigonometry since it came out that they were able to rate the materials as more than adequate to meet their needs in coping with their difficulties towards that field in Mathematics.

Bonitez (2021) drawn a conclusion based on the finding of the research, wherein the post-test of learners exposed to the teacher made SIM were remarkably better.

Based on the findings of the study of Gabucan and Sanchez (2021), the Strategic Intervention Material (SIM)-Based Teaching is a more effective approach in improving students' performance in the concepts of Global Warming in Science.

Ordoñez, Morauda, and Labini (2021) created a mobile assisted SIM wherein the study claims to have significant difference on learners using their SIM. With the help of the developed mobile assisted SIM, the learners show significant difference on their pre-test and post-test mean.

Bastida and Bastida (2022) further reiterated the use of SIM in teaching could increase the learning outcomes of students in science. Thus, recommending that, science teachers may develop and integrate the use of SIM in teaching difficult science concepts to low achieving learners through their in-service training (INSET).

Furthermore, Acera (2022) generously implements the Strategic Intervention Material in Science (SIM-S) to her learners with the found least mastered learning competencies in science, the researcher saw that a respectable number of learners have shown significant improvement in their academic performance.

With the evidence and research, the researcher is aiming for the higher grounds. Developing an intervention material is no easy task. The focus of this study will be the

Grade 11 Learners of Don Gaudencio B. Dumlao National High School, Aguilar, Pangasinan for the S.Y. 2023 – 2024.

Research Questions

The main goal of this study is to improve the Science Literacy of Grade 11 learners of Don Gaudencio B. Dumlao National High School on selected topic in Earth and Life Science through electronic SIM (e-SIM).

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following:

1. How may the Science Literacy on Selected Topic in Earth and Life Science among Grade 11 Learners be described?
2. How may the developed electronic SIM (e-SIM) have perceived by the Grade 11 learners?
3. Is there a significant difference in the science literacy of Grade 11 Senior High School learners on selected topic in Earth and Life Science before and after the intervention of electronic SIM (e-SIM)?

METHODOLOGY

A. Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 11 Senior High School Students of Don Gaudencio B. Dumlao National High School for the School Year 2023 – 2024.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The pre- test will be conducted to measure the science literacy of the learners in selected topic in Earth and Life Science before giving the developed intervention material. Thus, the post-test will be conducted to scale the science literacy of the learners in selected topic in Earth and Life Science after implementing the developed e-SIM.

The data gathered was subjected to the following statistical analysis.

For research question 1, the result of the pretest was used to answer the science literacy level of the respondents. Frequency and percentage analysis will be employed.

For research question 2, weighted mean was used to determine the student perception on the developed e-SIM.

For research question 3, t-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference among the pretest and post-test. T-test is an inferential statistical test used to decide if there is a significant difference between two groups and how these two groups are related. Hence, t-test is often used in hypothesis testing to figure out a whether a process or treatment has an effect.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-test and Post Test

Student	Pre-Test	Post Test
1	4	7
2	5	8
3	4	8
4	3	7
5	4	9
6	3	10
7	5	8
8	2	7
9	6	7
10	8	10
11	8	9
12	5	8
13	6	7
14	4	8
15	6	10
16	7	8
17	4	6
18	7	8
19	8	9
20	5	10
21	4	8
22	7	8
23	6	9
24	5	8
25	3	9

The table shows the pre-test and post results of the respondents. With the data presented, the table shows that out of 25 Grade 11 respondents, 4% (1 learner) got 2 on the pretest, 12% (3 students) got 3, 24% (6 students) got 4, 20% (5 students) got 5, 16% (4 students) got 6, 12% (3 students) got 7, and 12% (3 students) got 8. No learner got a perfect score during the pretest.

After the implementation of e-SIM, students' score significantly increased. As shown on the table, four (4) students obtained a perfect score.

Student Perception

Criteria	MEAN	DESCRIPTION
The e-SIM helps me understand the concept of landslide and how human activities triggers or speeds up landslide.	4.23	Excellent

Confusing concept of landslides and factors that speeds up or trigger landslides was clearly presented.	4.49	Excellent
The instructions are simple and easy to follow.	4.29	Excellent
The e-SIM is student-friendly material	4.00	Good
After using the e-SIM, I learn the concepts that were not fully understood in the distance modular instruction.	4.17	Good
I enjoyed doing all the activities provided in the e-SIM.	4.06	Good
I can set up my own pace in learning without feeling pressured about time.	4.06	Good
The e-SIM inspired and encouraged me to learn more concepts in Earth and Life Science.	4.25	Excellent
I want to use e-SIM during remediation class.	4.23	Excellent
Overall Mean	4.20	Good

Adapted from Mary Grace Cinco (2018)

Table shows the result of the developed electronic Strategic Intervention Material on Selected Topic in Earth and Life Science based on students' perception. With an overall mean of 4.20 and descriptive interpretation of **good**, the students find the developed e-SIM as valid and useful intervention material. Thus, students perceived that the developed SIM could bridge the learning gap on the selected topic in Earth and Life Science.

Moreover, the students also perceived that the developed e-SIM can be used as intervention materials. Based on the table, students also perceived that the developed SIMs could help them learn more concepts in Earth and Life at their own pace.

With the outcome of the study of Sinco (2018), with the use of SIM, students find it enjoyable, interesting and it contributes cheerful outlook towards learning more concepts in science. Furthermore, with the study presented by Romero (2021) learner had a lot of fun and they said that they enjoyed answering the material.

In addition, based on the study conducted by Acedillo et al., (2022), the most common subject from the perceptions with regards to the use of Strategic Intervention Material in science, is that SIM used to aid the least learned competencies of the learners. Furthermore, the researchers added that Strategic Intervention Material is simplified in terms of contents and approach as compared to normal classroom discussions.

Likewise, Creatrix Campus reiterated that learners actively involved in self-paced learning gets thirst to learn more about the topic, digging into deeper knowledge and willing to try out new and exciting learning perspective and environment.

Thus, Patterson (2015) said that self-paced learning makes learners more efficient and effective in a way that everyone can work on his own time to meet the learning goals and distribute more time on difficult materials.

Similarly, the study of Asio and Jimenez (2020) showed that remediation intervention has significant impact on the academic performance of Grade V learners. Thus, Sudhakar (2018) further said that remedial teachers should adapt the curriculum to accommodate the learning characteristics and abilities of pupils. Teachers should set some aims which are easy to achieve to ensure that learners may acquire the knowledge as preferred after the completion of each module or learning material.

t-test		
	Pre-Test	Post Test
Mean	5.16	8.24
Variance	2.89	1.19
Observations	25	25
Pearson Correlation	0.292984029	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	24	
t Stat	-8.901089746	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.00000000226831	
t Critical one-tail	1.71088208	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00000000453663	
t Critical two-tail	2.063898562	

It can be gleaned from the result of the post test that there is a significant difference on the scientific literacy of Grade 11 learners of Don Gaudencio B. Dumlao National High School on selected topic in Earth and Life Science. Thus, the result shows that the *p value* is equal to 0.00000000453663, therefore accepting the fact that there is a significant difference on the scientific literacy of Grade 11 of Don Gaudencio B. Dumlao National High School.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, the following conclusions were drawn

1. The application of electronic Strategic Intervention Material (eSIM) showed a significant increase in their pre-test and post-test scores. With the developed eSIM, the researcher and teachers may now have learning material that can be used as an intervention for struggling learners.

2. In terms of student perception, the developed electronic Strategic Intervention Materials (eSIM) on Selected Topics in Earth and Life Science are considerably good. Therefore, students gleaned that the developed eSIM can really help them understand complex topics at their own pace and give them another venture of learning.
3. With the application of eSIM on the lesson, learners showed a significant difference on their scientific literacy. Based on the computed p value, the developed eSIM significantly increased the scientific literacy of the Grade 11 learners.

Recommendations

1. Since the eSIM demonstrated a significant difference and improvement of pre-test and post-test scores, the researcher recommended that teachers should consider the use of eSIM across various science topics. Future studies may be conducted to test its effectiveness in other subject areas.
2. Customization of the developed electronic SIM to cater different learning styles of the learners, and expansion of the topics would provide learners with more learning options, allowing them to engage more with the lesson at their own pace.
3. Considering the significant effect of the developed eSIM, future research could explore the eSIM's integration in blended learning – combining the face-to-face instruction with digital integration. With this, learners may experience more holistic learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from the students and their guardians, outlining the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Participants were assured that their responses would remain confidential and anonymous, and that the data collected would be used solely for academic and research purposes. The study did not involve any physical or psychological risks, and participants were free to withdraw from the research at any point without any negative consequences. Furthermore, the research adhered to institutional guidelines for ethical conduct in research and was reviewed and approved by the appropriate ethics review board to ensure adherence to ethical principles in educational research, such as respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

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